

Figure 1: Heatmap of emission contribution by region

Figure 2: GHG Emission sources in the HCS

Regional Energy Consumption Patterns

Figure 3: Regional energy consumption pattern

Figure 4: Carbon footprint by category across regions

Figure 5: Total average carbon footprint by region

Figure 6: Carbon footprint component by region

Figure 7: Bar charts showing various analyzed variables for carbon footprint

Figure 8: Contribution to CO₂ footprint by category

Figure 9: Mean monthly HCS Spending

Figure 10: Percentage income spent on heating /HCS (monthly)

Figure 11: Building stock efficiency heatmap

Figure 12: Regional climate adaptation timeline

Housing Efficiency vs Emissions

Darker colors indicate higher heat loss, text shows retrofit potential

Figure 13: Housing efficiency vs emission

Regional CO₂ Emissions & Policy Priorities

Bars: Total CO₂ | Diamonds: Rosstat Tariff Deviation

Figure 14: Regional CO₂ emissions vs policy priorities